

Characteristics of waxy and nonwaxy isogenic lines.^a Hangzhou, China, 1987.

Character	Guangluai 4			Yuanfengzao			Zhenzhu 19		
	Waxy	Nonwaxy	Difference	Waxy	Nonwaxy	Difference	Waxy	Nonwaxy	Difference
Plant ht (cm)	76.10	75.88	0.22	80.45	78.08	2.37*	93.28	91.43	1.85
<i>Rough rice</i>									
1000-grain wt (g)	21.40	23.08	-1.68**	18.05	19.60	-1.55**	28.30	31.35	-3.05**
Grain length (mm)	6.97	6.80	0.17*	6.19	6.70	0.09	8.70	8.71	-0.01
Specific gravity of grain (g/ml)	0.99	1.10	-0.11**	1.02	1.10	-0.08**	1.04	1.12	-0.08**
Percentage rough rice	78.83	80.15	-1.32**	79.10	80.44	-1.34*	80.74	82.47	-1.73**
<i>Brown rice</i>									
Length (mm)	5.24	5.42	-0.18*	5.13	5.36	-0.23**	6.83	7.13	-0.30**
Width (mm)	2.73	2.89	-0.16*	2.35	2.57	-0.22**	2.62	2.84	-0.22**
Thickness (mm)	1.94	2.03	-0.09*	1.92	1.98	-0.06*	2.06	2.11	-0.05**
Size (mm ³)	27.81	31.83	-4.02**	23.10	26.98	-3.88**	36.80	42.64	-5.84**
1000-grain wt (g)	17.72	20.34	-2.62**	15.64	17.41	-1.77**	23.86	27.50	-3.64**

^a* and ** = significance at the 5% and 1% levels.

Grain quality and nutritional value

Rice varietal differences in number of brokens

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Rice varietal differences in grain form, size, and weight affect percentage of brokens after milling. That determines milling recovery, percentage of head rice, and price.

We measured moisture content of 36 varieties and lines, then hulled 140-g grain samples with a small Satake rubber roll rice hulling machine (THU 35 A). The experiment design was completely randomized with four replications.

Of the varieties tested, 13 had more than 80% head rice (see table). Among them are four lines not yet released—M61b-28-3-5, IR4427-85-2-1, B4180F-30-NG-4-2, and IR4427-5-6-3. IR56 had the lowest head rice percentage.□

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Head rice recovery of 36 varieties and lines.^a Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia, 1985-86 dry season.

Variety	Rough rice moisture content (%)	Brown rice (%)	
		Head rice (%)	Brokens (%)
M61b-28-3-5	13.5	91.4 a	6.7 a
Barito	13.3	86.6 a	7.7 a
IR26	13.3	87.5 a	8.1 b
IR4427-85-2-1	13.5	87.3 a	8.5 b
Semeru	12.3	77.4 ab	10.2 b
Cisadane	13.5	88.0 a	10.3 b
Kelara	15.1	79.8 ab	10.4 b
Bogowonto	14.2	84.7 a	11.7 b
IR46	13.5	85.2 a	12.5 bc
Batang Agam	14.3	84.2 a	12.6 bc
Krueng Aceh	13.2	82.4 a	12.6 bc
Sadang	13.8	84.5 a	12.7 bc
B4180F-30-NG-4-2	13.6	83.4 a	13.8 c
BR319-11-HR12	11.9	77.6 ab	14.4 c
Cipunegara	14.2	82.5 a	14.4 c
M12C-34-3	14.2	78.4 ab	15.7 c
IR4427-5-6-3	12.8	80.3 a	16.2 c
BR-5 1-282-8	14.3	79.1 ab	17.4 c
Citarum	12.4	77.3 b	17.8 c
IR36	12.9	77.7 ab	17.7 c
BR-IRGA-409	13.9	77.6 ab	18.1 c
Cikapundung	14.6	77.7 ab	19.7 cd
GH2 18	14.3	76.2 b	21.0 d
IR4425-85-2-1	14.1	87.3 a	21.2 d
Cimandiri	14.9	72.6 b	21.4 d
B5322b-Pn-1-MS-1-KP-1	14.9	75.7 b	22.2 d
IR5 0	12.5	72.6 b	23.1 d
IR30	11.6	71.2 b	23.3 d
IR22082-41-2	14.1	71.6 b	24.9 d
IR58	13.9	70.3 b	26.5 de
IR28	10.8	68.0 c	26.9 e
IR54	12.8	66.2 c	27.9 e
IR60	12.7	66.9 b	27.9 e
IR5 2	11.9	61.9 c	33.0 e
B40706-NG-2	12.7	61.0 c	35.6 ef
IR56	11.0	53.1 c	44.0 f

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.